

Mapping via \mathcal{S}^1 -Regularization

Mapping via \mathbb{R}^2 -Regularization

Fig S2. Comparison of virtual marker mappings obtained with different regularization schemes. On the left hand side, \mathcal{S}^1 -regularization was used in which neighboring virtual markers are regularized w.r.t their normalized arc length coordinates. On the right hand side, the \mathbb{R}^2 -distances of neighboring virtual markers is used for regularization. While the \mathbb{R}^2 -regularization fails during large shape deformations, producing wide gaps between virtual markers and topological mapping violations (red lines), satisfying contour mappings are provided by the \mathcal{S}^1 -regularization as used by our method.